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LEARNING HAS NO END - LIFELONG LEARNING COMPETENCES FOR ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Lifelong learning (LLL) has become an integral part of professional life. Universities have to make their students aware of their professional identity and train them in continuously re-inventing themselves. Lifelong learning, however, is complex and requires a variety of personal resources. In this exploratory study the aim is to get an overview of the current LLL competences of engineering students at the Faculty of Engineering Technology, KU Leuven and the Faculty of Applied Engineering, University of Antwerp. In order to achieve this, a generic lifelong learning scale developed by Kirby et al. (2010) is used. A small, but significant, difference between the LLL competences of bachelor and master students is found.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Lifelong learning (LLL) has become an integral part of professional life. Continuously updating and up-skilling of competences is necessary in order to keep pace with the changing requirements of the labour market [1,2]. Looking more specifically at engineers, the half-life of an engineer's technical knowledge is limited to two to seven years depending on the discipline [3]. Higher education institutions have a leading role in delivering engineers with lifelong learning competences. Universities have to make their students aware of their professional identity and train them in continuously re-inventing themselves. As stated by [4] lifelong learning is a key aspect for future engineering education. Lifelong learning competencies, however, are complex and can be described by different definitions. For example, a recent study [5] identified the following four factors having an effect on the lifelong learning of students: curiosity, openness to learning, access to information and information literacy, and self-direction and self-evaluation. Another study [6] distinguished six subscales: self-management competencies, learning how to learn competencies, initiative and entrepreneur competencies, competencies of acquiring information, digital competencies, and decision-taking competencies. De Keyzer et al. [7] stated that for lifelong learning, students should have (1) the willingness to look out for and take advantage of learning occasions, (2) the ability to do self-direct learning (set goals, plan and execute, (re)evaluate and draw learning gains) and (3) knowledge of means to do so [7]. The openness for developing lifelong learning skills is bound to be determined by the attitude of students as well as the students' self-esteem regarding those skills. In other words: self-regulated learning (SRL) is a key factor for lifelong learning.

In this study the aim is to get an overview of the current LLL competences of engineering students at the Faculty of Engineering Technology, KU Leuven, and the Faculty of Applied Engineering, University of Antwerp. Though the names of these faculties suggest a differing nature, they educate towards the same master degree. Comparing both faculties goes beyond the scope of this study. Consequently, the participants are combined into one sample.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Instrument

In order to measure the LLL competences of students, a questionnaire developed by [8] is used. Their generic lifelong learning scale, consisting of 14 items, focuses on the following constructs [9]: (1) Goal setting, (2) Application of knowledge and skills, (3) Self-direction and evaluation, (4) Locating information, (5) Adaptable learning strategies. The questionnaire is self-reported and participants are asked to answer on a five-point Likert scale (1= Totally disagree and 5= Totally agree). In their study [8] the Cronbach alpha was 0.71, which is considered as a reasonable reliability, especially since lifelong learning is a complex construct. The factor analysis resulted in one single factor.

2.2 Sample

The link for the online LLL questionnaire is distributed to 2nd year bachelor's, 3rd year bachelor's, transfer students, and master students of the Faculty of Engineering Technology, KU Leuven, and the Faculty of Applied Engineering, University of Antwerp. Participation in the study was voluntary and completely anonymous. A total of 160 engineering students completed the online survey.

2.3 Hypotheses

In this study two main hypotheses are formulated below:

- Hypothesis 1: Master students obtain a higher level of LLL competences than bachelor students.
- Hypothesis 2: There is no difference in the LLL competences of master students that followed the regular study programme and the ones that entered the master's programme via the transfer programme (i.e. an alternative pathway).

The next section includes, besides the outcomes of the hypotheses, descriptive statistics and the internal consistency of the survey.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Summary and descriptive statistics

Table 1 shows the distribution of the students' answer for each of the 14 items. The descriptive statistics of the items are presented in Table 2. The mean sum score of the LLL survey is 3.37 (SD=.32).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics and item-total correlations (Rit) LLL survey

Lifelong Learning items		Mean	SD	Rit
Q1r	I prefer to have others plan my learning	2.93	.935	.074
Q2r	I prefer problems for which there is only one solution	3.42	.921	.223
Q3	I can deal with the unexpected and solve problems as they arise	3.91	.558	.253
Q4r	I feel uncomfortable under conditions of uncertainty	2.56	.845	.201
Q5	I am able to impose meaning upon what others see as disorder	3.54	.751	.177
Q6r	I seldom think about my own learning and how to improve it	3.09	1.15	-.001
Q7	I feel I am a self-directed learner	3.60	.856	.219
Q8r	I feel others are in a better position than I am to evaluate my success as a student	3.28	.951	.149
Q9	I love learning for its own sake	3.36	1.01	.418
Q10	I try to relate academic learning to practical issues	3.84	.765	.281
Q11r	I often find it difficult to locate information when I need it	3.04	.924	.314
Q12	When I approach new material, I try to relate it to what I already know	3.94	.741	.235
Q13	It is my responsibility to make sense of what I learn at school	3.38	.923	.100
Q14r	When I learn something new I try to focus on the details rather than on the 'big picture'	3.37	.895	-.037

Table 2. Answer distribution – Merged Likert scale: 1&2= disagree, 3= neutral, 4&5= agree *Note. r=reversed item*

Lifelong learning items	Bachelor students (N=82)				Transfer students (N=13)				Master students (N=65)				Total (N=160)			
	disagree	neutral	agree	N	disagree	neutral	agree	N	disagree	neutral	agree	N	disagree	neutral	agree	N
Q1r I prefer to have others plan my learning	24 (29%)	28 (34%)	30 (37%)	30	4 (31%)	9 (69%)	0 (0%)	0	19 (29%)	16 (25%)	30 (46%)	30	47 (29%)	53 (33%)	60 (38%)	60
Q2r I prefer problems for which there is only one solution	42 (51%)	23 (28%)	17 (21%)	17	5 (38%)	4 (31%)	4 (31%)	4	40 (62%)	18 (28%)	7 (11%)	7	87 (54%)	45 (28%)	28 (18%)	28
Q3 I can deal with the unexpected and solve problems as they arise	3 (4%)	11 (13%)	68 (83%)	68	0 (0%)	3 (23%)	10 (77%)	10	2 (3%)	4 (6%)	59 (91%)	59	5 (3%)	18 (11%)	137 (86%)	137
Q4r I feel uncomfortable under conditions of uncertainty	11 (13%)	24 (29%)	47 (57%)	47	2 (15%)	3 (23%)	8 (62%)	8	11 (17%)	24 (37%)	30 (46%)	30	24 (15%)	51 (32%)	85 (53%)	85
Q5 I am able to impose meaning upon what others see as disorder	8 (10%)	29 (35%)	45 (55%)	45	0 (0%)	7 (54%)	6 (46%)	6	2 (3%)	23 (35%)	40 (62%)	40	10 (6%)	59 (37%)	91 (57%)	91
Q6r I seldom think about my own learning and how to improve	43 (52%)	11 (13%)	28 (34%)	28	5 (38%)	3 (23%)	5 (38%)	5	29 (45%)	11 (17%)	25 (38%)	25	77 (48%)	25 (16%)	58 (36%)	58
Q7 I feel I am a self-directed learner	10 (12%)	24 (29%)	48 (59%)	48	3 (23%)	6 (46%)	4 (31%)	4	5 (8%)	13 (20%)	47 (72%)	47	18 (11%)	43 (27%)	99 (62%)	99
Q8r I feel others are in a better position than I am to evaluate my success as a student	35 (43%)	26 (32%)	21 (26%)	21	4 (31%)	3 (23%)	6 (46%)	6	34 (52%)	20 (31%)	11 (17%)	11	73 (46%)	49 (31%)	38 (24%)	38
Q9 I love learning for its own sake	19 (23%)	29 (35%)	34 (41%)	34	0 (0%)	5 (38%)	8 (62%)	8	8 (12%)	17 (26%)	40 (62%)	40	27 (17%)	51 (32%)	82 (51%)	82
Q10 I try to relate academic learning to practical issues	5 (6%)	20 (24%)	57 (70%)	57	1 (8%)	0 (0%)	12 (92%)	12	3 (5%)	11 (17%)	51 (78%)	51	9 (6%)	31 (19%)	120 (75%)	120
Q11r I often find it difficult to locate information when I need it	32 (39%)	30 (37%)	20 (24%)	20	7 (54%)	3 (23%)	3 (23%)	3	18 (28%)	18 (28%)	29 (45%)	29	57 (36%)	51 (32%)	52 (33%)	52
Q12 When I approach new material, I try to relate it to what I already know	3 (4%)	16 (20%)	63 (77%)	63	0 (0%)	1 (8%)	12 (92%)	12	4 (6%)	8 (12%)	53 (82%)	53	7 (4%)	25 (16%)	128 (80%)	128
Q13 It is my responsibility to make sense of what I learn at school	16 (20%)	28 (34%)	38 (46%)	38	1 (8%)	2 (15%)	10 (77%)	10	14 (22%)	17 (26%)	34 (52%)	34	31 (19%)	47 (29%)	82 (51%)	82
Q14r When I learn something new I try to focus on the details rather than on the 'big picture'	40 (49%)	20 (24%)	22 (27%)	22	7 (54%)	5 (38%)	1 (8%)	1	38 (58%)	19 (29%)	8 (12%)	8	85 (53%)	44 (28%)	31 (19%)	31

3.2 Internal consistency

This study found a Cronbach's Alpha of .52, which is below the required .70 to be considered as acceptable. The interpretation of the item-total correlations (Rit) according to the thumb rules of Ebel [10]: poor ($Rit < 0.20$), doubtful ($0.21 < Rit < 0.29$), good ($0.30 < Rit < 0.39$), and very good ($Rit > 0.40$), resulted in six poor, six doubtful, one good, and one very good item (Table 2).

3.3 Differences in LLL competences

Performing an ANOVA² analysis showed no significant differences between the different groups of students ($F=1.260$, $p=.288$). An independent samples T-test³ was conducted between the regular master students and master students who entered the programme via an alternative pathway and no significant difference was found ($T=.124$, $p=.902$).

Table 3. Lifelong learning for different student groups

LLL for different student groups	N	Mean	SD
2 nd year bachelor's	38	3.32	.268
3 rd year bachelor's	44	3.32	.334
Transfer	13	3.40	.257
Master's	43	3.43	.346
Master's via transfer programme	22	3.44	.348
Total	160	3.37	.320

The students were also merged into two groups: bachelor students ($M=3.32$, $SD=.303$, $N=82$) and master students ($M=3.44$, $SD=.344$, $N=65$). An independent samples T-test⁴ showed a significant difference between the two groups ($T=2.20$, $p=.029$). Appendix A presents the mean scores for each individual item for both the bachelor and master students.

By way of comparison, we compared our results ($M=3.37$, $SD=.320$, $N=160$) with the ones in the original paper ($M=3.72$, $SD=.410$, $N=309$) [8] and conducted an independent samples T-test. This showed a significant higher mean score for the pilot in the original study ($T=9.413$, $p<.0001$). Since the original study [8] included only final year students, the same analysis is performed with only the master students ($M=3.44$, $SD=.344$, $N=65$), which also resulted in a significant difference ($T= 5.145$, $p<.0001$).

^{2,3,4} Levene's test showed that homogeneity of variances can be assumed.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Hypotheses

A small, but significant, difference between the LLL competences of bachelor and master students is found, which is in line with hypothesis 1, namely that master students achieve a higher level of LLL competences. No statements, however, can be made about how many students have appropriate LLL competences. It will be important to define in further research (1) what determines appropriate LLL competences and (2) what will be the threshold to make a distinction between 'inadequate' and 'proper' LLL competences. In comparison to the original study [8], the participants in our study obtained a significant lower mean score on the LLL survey. This is an indication that Flemish Engineering students possess a lower level of LLL competences, which will be further examined in future work.

It is reassuring that there are no differences in LLL competences between regular master students and master students who entered the programme via an alternative pathway. After all, it is important that at the end, all graduates obtain similar LLL competences, regardless of their study pathway. At the end of the study programme, similar learning outcomes are pursued irrespectively of the students' study pathway.

4.2 Individual items

Given the exploratory character of the study and the low consistency within the questionnaire, it is worthwhile to analyse some of the questions separately.

For instance, only a third of the participants (29%, N=47) prefer to plan their own learning (Q1). Even in the final year, only 29% (N=19) of the master students prefer to plan their own learning. Almost half of the master students (46%, N=30) prefer to have others plan their learning, while 25% (N=16) are undecided. In addition, 36% of the total group (N=58) indicate that they only seldom think about their own learning and how they can improve it (Q6). Both these results can be an indication that there is not enough awareness of the importance of lifelong learning among students. An important element, when fostering students' LLL attitude, will be to focus on increasing the awareness of the importance of LLL [11]. In another study [12] focus group discussions, organised with faculties organizing programmes in Engineering Technology at the Flemish universities, showed that all universities acknowledge the great importance of LLL. They also point out that a possible manner to increase students' awareness is to include LLL more explicitly in the study programme. Introducing a LLL course in which each individual student (N=17) had to make a personal development plan, is one manner to make LLL more explicit [7]. Almost all the students (N=15, 88%) reported that they have learned to set goals, to self-assess and continuously (re)-evaluate their learning. Although they attribute the latter two abilities mostly to the entire curriculum, more than half of the students assign learning to set goals to the specific LLL course. In addition, 12 students state that they now

have the willingness to look out for formal, non-formal, and informal opportunities for further self-development.

A large majority of the participants in this study state that they try to relate (1) academic learning to practical issues (Q10, N=120, 75%) and (2) new material to what they already know (Q12, N=128, 80%). Also 86% (N=137) of the participants indicate that they feel comfortable tackling unexpected problems (Q3). These items seem to be related to direct problem-solving areas that are relevant for engineers. They might indicate that engineering students are capable of learning 'on the job' when the learning opportunity passes their path. This is a contrast to the 'planned' learning where a person would not only learn for the moment, but set up a plan for learning in order to tackle future problems (cfr. Q1 and Q6).

Surprisingly enough master students find it significantly more difficult to locate information (Q11) than bachelor students ($T=2.073$, $p=.040$). This might be due to master students being confronted with the difficulty of finding information for their master thesis or challenging project work. However, further and more in-depth research is required. With the exception of items Q1 and Q11, all other items seem to indicate an increase from bachelor to master, which is in line with hypothesis 1. The increase however is only significant for Q2: "*I prefer problems for which there is only one solution*" ($T=-2.378$, $p=.019$) and Q9: "*I love learning for its own sake*" ($T=2.204$, $p=.029$). 62% of the master students (N=40) state that they do not prefer problems for which there is only one solution and 28% (N=18) answers neutral on this item. This, of course, is a relief, since engineering problems rarely have one exact solution.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This exploratory study found significant higher scores on LLL competences for master students, which confirms one of the hypotheses of the research. The sample of this study, however, obtains significant lower scores than the sample of the study of which the survey was used [8]. The low internal consistency of the survey has to be studied in more detail since it is in conflict with the original paper [8]. Including LLL more explicitly can be a possible manner to increase the awareness for the importance of LLL as demonstrated by [7]. In future work it will be determined what the LLL concept means to the engineering profession. The results of another study [12] are the starting point. Student background variables were not taken into account in this study. It is however plausible that there are differences when they are included. In further research we will therefore control for background variables.

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APPENDIX A

Table 4. Mean item scores for bachelor (N=82) and master students (N=65)

Mean item scores		Mean	SD
Q1	Master students	3.15	.988
	Bachelor students	3.08	.940
Q2	Master students	2.35	.856
	Bachelor students	2.71	.944
Q3	Master students	3.98	.545
	Bachelor students	3.86	.566
Q4	Master students	3.37	.858
	Bachelor students	3.51	.846
Q5	Master students	3.66	.735
	Bachelor students	3.46	.786
Q6	Master students	2.98	1.12
	Bachelor students	2.83	1.17
Q7	Master students	3.75	.811
	Bachelor students	3.57	.872
Q8	Master students	2.58	.900
	Bachelor students	2.78	.969
Q9	Master students	3.52	.970
	Bachelor students	3.16	1.03
Q10	Master students	3.94	.808
	Bachelor students	3.76	.742
Q11	Master students	3.15	.972
	Bachelor students	2.84	.848
Q12	Master students	4.00	.848
	Bachelor students	3.87	.677
Q13	Master students	3.37	.993
	Bachelor students	3.31	.869
Q14	Master students	2.51	.812
	Bachelor students	2.75	.935